
Improvement of Warehouse Classification and Service in Logistics Infrastructure

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Abstract: This article discusses the improvement of warehouses and services in the logistics infrastructure. The features of the logistics approach to organizing warehouse processes and the criteria for their effectiveness, logistics tools for managing them are identified. The logistics functions of the warehouse and the conditions for achieving a high level of profitability of its operation are determined.

Key words: warehouse, logistics functions, logistics process, warehouse logistics system, infrastructure.

In modern conditions, the growing role of and interest in logistics are due to the needs of business development, the possibilities of increasing the efficiency of material handling systems. Movement of material flows in the logistics chain is impossible without concentration of the necessary stocks in certain places, for storage of which the corresponding warehouses are intended. The logistics approach to the organization of warehouse processes provides a competitive advantage for the company and the entire supply chain, since the warehouse is its important element and a component with the potential for reducing costs [2].

The logistics functions of warehouses are implemented in the process of implementing individual logistics operations as elementary logistics activities - a separate set of actions aimed at transforming the material and / or information flow and not subject to further decomposition within the framework of the task. They are determined by the initial conditions and parameters of the external environment.

Warehouse operations are aimed at ensuring the safety of stored goods, creating convenience for their error-free and quick selection, efficient use of warehouse space. Implementation of the stock function means the need to carry out work on placing goods for storage, ensuring the necessary storage conditions and removing goods from storage locations [1]. The transformation of material flows occurs through the disbanding of some cargo lots or cargo units and the formation of others. This means the need to unpack cargo, assemble new cargo units, pack them and fill them. Compliance with the scheme of goods release (receiving orders, selecting goods from storage areas, moving to the order assembly area, order assembly and packing, route assembly of lots, moving completed lots to the loading area, loading transport) and the coordination of the warehouse personnel contribute to the fulfillment of customer orders and the enhancement of the business reputation and prestige of the enterprise itself.

The logistics process in a warehouse is the management of logistics operations related to cargo handling and the coordination of related services that ensure the efficient functioning of the warehouse (Fig. 1). It is clear from the figure that the process is complex, since it requires the coordination of stock supply, cargo handling and physical distribution of orders.

Fig. 1. Logistics operations in the warehouse

For this reason, it includes stock supply and control over deliveries, unloading and acceptance of goods, intra-warehouse transportation and transshipment of goods, their warehousing and storage, picking, transportation and expedition of customer orders, ensuring their servicing, information services for the warehouse, collection and delivery of empty goods carriers, is broader than the technological process. Warehouse activity as part of an integrated logistics system is a limiting link that causes additional errors, therefore it is necessary to identify and solve problems to improve warehouse logistics operations. It is necessary to implement virtual and augmented reality technologies to improve the efficiency of warehouse operations and eliminate their "bottlenecks" [3]. For each specific warehouse, the parameters of the warehouse system differ from each other, so only an individual solution taking into account all the influencing factors can make the warehouse system profitable, and the costs - economically justified.

A rationally organized warehouse process takes into account the specifics and speed of operations, guarantees the safety of inventory items, minimizes costs and has a high level of logistics service. It must comply with the principles of organization in practice: proportionality (coordination of related operations occurring in the warehouse), parallelism (simultaneous execution of individual operations at all stages of work), rhythm (repetition of cycles) and direct flow (reduction of idle movement of transport in the warehouse). The key to process management in the context of innovative economic development is the transparency of warehouse operations (without documented warehouse processes and clear work instructions, the manager cannot control the quality of work). The manager is responsible for the performance of all work by warehouse personnel and ensuring the growth of their labor productivity. The stages of personnel management as a source of competitive advantages of the company are associated with the growth

model, which determines the actions of the manager at different stages of warehouse development (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Stages of warehouse development and management

The data in Fig. 2 indicate that at the lead stage, savings are achieved through competent planning and efficient use of resources, and at the cooperation stage, through the coordination of actions of the links in the logistics chain and high integration of its participants. Taking into account and analyzing changes in competitive environment factors and using logistics tools for managing the company's warehouse operations contribute to achieving high profitability of warehouse operations, obtaining a synergistic effect, as well as implementing and developing long-term competitive advantages [2].

To optimize the logistics process, it is necessary to systematically assess the effectiveness of activities based on key indicators characterizing the warehouse cargo flow and the degree of utilization of its area (cargo flow per day, per day for receipts and shipments, per day for in-house processing; coefficient of in-house transshipments, warehouse utilization, unevenness in the receipt of goods; warehouse turnover, its throughput capacity) (Table 1).

Table 1. Indicators of the efficiency of the functioning of the warehouse complex and logistics processes in the warehouse

Performance indicators of the warehouse complex	Key factors	Performance indicators of the logistics process in the warehouse
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Ratio of the number of orders completed on time to the total number of requests * Ratio of incomplete deliveries to the number of requests * Cost of warehouse services and the number of complaints about them 	Degree of satisfaction of warehouse services consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Ensuring order fulfillment exactly by the specified deadline * Completeness of order satisfaction * Accuracy of order parameters * Accuracy of maintaining inventory levels * Number of order returns
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Order fulfillment time 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Time for processing,

* Time for replenishing stocks, preparing and completing orders	Logistics cycle time, order cycle	preparing and completing consumer orders * Order delivery time * Order fulfillment time
* Warehouse throughput and turnover * Order fulfillment rate * Warehouse volume (area) utilization and warehouse mechanization * Compliance with internal warehouse operating procedures (damage)	Quality of warehouse work and warehouse service	* Errors in order fulfillment * Cases of loss, theft, damage * Return of goods by customers * Consumer complaints and their assessment of the degree of satisfaction with the service * Speed and quantity of inventory turnover * Use of working capital
* Inventory turnover * Average warehouse inventory level * Number of cargo handling operations per day * Costs of cargo handling, packaging and other services	Evaluation of warehouse complex resources, logistics costs, use of investments	* Logistics costs per unit of capital invested in warehouse stocks, per unit of warehouse turnover * Average level of stocks in the warehouse * Use of investments in technological equipment * Costs of inventory management, cargo handling, ensuring the quality of warehouse service, storage

Despite the fact that software and information tasks in the overall structure of enterprise problems occupy an insignificant share (8.33%), their solution is currently given much attention. Modern WMS (Warehouse Management System), with powerful accounting and configuration functions, is an automated warehouse management information system that provides comprehensive automation of the entire warehouse economy [4].

The purpose of its implementation is to increase the transparency of warehouse operations and reduce management resources; Typical tasks are operational informing about operations carried out in the warehouse, managing the structure of warehouse areas, automation of managing the procedures for receiving and storing goods, automatic tracking of the correctness of accounting for data on the quantity and nomenclature of storage units, managing the work of the warehouse using software and hardware solutions. Management automation in WMS systems is based on targeted storage technologies, automatic identification of storage, goods, equipment and warehouse personnel using barcodes or radio interpreters (Table 2).

Table 2. Technologies used in modern WMS

TECHNOLOGY, SYSTEM	THE CONTENT OF THE TECHNOLOGY
RFID – Radio frequency identification	Radio frequency identification. The system of automatic identification of goods, storage and equipment.
RF/DC – Radio frequency/ Data communication	Mobile wireless data transmission systems on the radio channel.
DCC – Data capture and collection	Mobility manual computers (terminals) for

	collecting data by scanning marks. Mobile workplace.
BT – Bluetooth; Wi-Fi – Wireless fidelity GSM/GPRS	Wireless data transmission and positioning technologies supported by modern Unitech, Intermec, etc. mobile computers.
VDT – Voice direct technologies	Technology and means of direct voice management of tasks
WCS – Warehouse control system	Product control system. Determining the mass and dimensions of the goods entering the storage/shipment
CWS – Cubing and weighing system	WCS component. Automatic definition of weight -and -power parameters of goods

The Warehouse Management System presented today in the market have different functionality, as they are guided by various industries. The effectiveness of the implementation of the system is affected not only by the choice of a particular program, but also by the practical skills of the experts of experts to understand the business processes of a particular enterprise and ensure the consistency of the function of the system with real activities.

The introduction of a WMS system leads to an increase in the productivity of warehouse processes, improve the structure of costs and reduce warehouse costs. The introduction of automatic technologies for 20 % of the warehouse allows you to process more than 70 % of the most time -consuming product on this area. Unfortunately, at present, 12 % of WMS companies is used at the functionality level by 80 % or more, and in 88 % of companies only within 15 % [5].

All groups of solutions to a logistics problem as a set of measures to reorganize and optimize the work of the warehouse are interconnected. First, it is necessary to analyze retrospective commodity flows and stocks with a forecast for the future period, consider the dimension of flows, structure, dynamics and turnover of orders. After this, it is required to formulate and “digitize” the requirements of the business for the warehouse, specify the composition of the operations performed, ensure the required storage conditions, the quality of operations and the cost of storage; only at the final stage - to evaluate the current state of the warehouse (volume -planning solutions, the state of warehouse infrastructure, volume, topology, organizational structure, technology used, system of accounting and management) and its “narrow places”.

Conducting an analysis of the problem and a circle of unresolved tasks precedes determining measures to achieve goals and solving the problem. They can touch both directly warehouse business processes (acceptance of goods, accommodation, equipment and shipment of orders, inventory, etc.), and related processes that implement the interaction of the warehouse and adjacent units (management of stocks, purchases of goods, organization deliveries of goods to a warehouse and delivery of customer orders).

Thus, the warehouse is an independent logistics system, the most important element of the supply chain and the link of modern network logistics structures. Properly organized logistics processes in the warehouse must correspond to the features and necessary parameters of warehouse operations, ensure the safety of stocks, cost -effectiveness and the optimal level of logistics service. From the effectiveness of warehouse operations and timely solving the problems of logistics in warehouse: organizational, frame, coordination, communicative, topological, technical, technological, program-information, the degree of achievement of organizational goals, the productive functioning of the warehouse, the success of these structures of enterprises and the competitiveness of chain.

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